

Performance of Different Machine Learning Algorithms in Rainfall Runoff Modelling Compared to the Conceptual Model PREVAH in Selected Swiss Catchments

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Benjamin Meyer
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Supervisor
Dr. Pascal Horton

Abstract

Numerous rainfall runoff models have been developed for different purposes over the past decades. Rainfall runoff models can be divided into three categories: physics-based models, conceptual models, and data-driven models. Recently, machine learning has become increasingly popular among the data-driven models. However, studies investigating the performance of machine learning algorithms in Swiss catchments are scarce. In this study, six different machine learning algorithms (XGBoost, LightGBM, MLP, LSTM, GRU, SVR) are used to build runoff models in 9 Swiss catchments. In addition, the effects of different calibration period lengths and main discharge generation processes are analysed. We were able to demonstrate the potential of machine learning for rainfall runoff modelling in Swiss catchments. XGBoost and LightGBM performed best, consistently achieving NSE values above 0.8, followed by SVR and MLP. LSTM and GRU performed the worst. Of the algorithms tested, SVR showed the greatest improvement with a longer calibration period. While our results do not consistently reach the performance of the benchmark study, we see room for further optimisation to possibly bring them on par. We also provide a simple overview of the strengths and weaknesses of the algorithms based on our results.

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List of Abbreviations

FOEN	Federal Office of Environment
GRU	Gated Recurrent Network
HP	Hyperparameter
HPO	Hyperparameter Optimisation
HRU	Hydrological Response Unit
KGE	Kling-Gupta Efficiency
LSTM	Long-Short-Term-Memory
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
ML	Machine learning
NMAE	Normalised Mean Absolute Error
NN	Neural Network
NRMSE	Normalised Root Mean Squared Error
NSE	Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency
r	Pearson correlation coefficient
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
RRM	Rainfall Runoff Model
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SVR	Support Vector Regression

1. Introduction

Our physical and economic well-being depends on the availability of water. More than half of the SDGs are, in one way or another, related to water resources. Sustainable management of water resources is a necessity to ensure everyone's access to water in sufficient quality and quantity, without harming the environment. But as important as water is, it is also a potential hazard. Flooding is just one example of how water can cause substantial damage, either directly or indirectly. The basis for effective risk management is accurate data. Knowing where, when, and how much water is available is fundamental. One of the key environmental variables for water resource management is discharge. While measurement is the foundation, it can only provide current and historical data. To gain insight into future conditions and make predictions, some form of modelling is required. This is where rainfall runoff models (RRM) come in.

Countless models have been developed over the past decades for different purposes, each with trade-offs in terms of degree of realism, data requirements, computational power needed and ease of use (Beven, 2011). RRM can be classified into three types: physics-based models that attempt to model the physical processes, conceptual models that are strongly simplified representations of the real world often based on a storage cascade, and finally data-driven models such as standard statistical models and, more recently, machine learning models (Sitterson et al., 2019). As their name suggests physics-based models are based on physical laws. They are very site specific and need very fine grain information about the physical properties of the site. As a result, they provide excellent spatial and often temporal resolution. Conceptual models on the other hand are much easier to calibrate, need less data, and often have a simple model structure. However, the spatial variability within the catchment is not represented as well as in physics-based model. The advantage of machine learning based models is the ability to “learn” from data and adapting to the dominant processes without the need for prior knowledge. Another advantage is the flexibility regarding the input variables and their temporal resolution. Drawbacks are the necessity of long timeseries to train the models as well as the lumped model structure giving no information about spatial variability within the catchment.

While it has been shown that machine learning models can outperform conceptual models in RRM (Kratzert et al., 2018; Szczepanek, 2022; Cui et al., 2021), at the time of writing this thesis, only one publication investigating the performance of machine learning models in Swiss catchments (Emme) could be found. Mohammadi et al. (2022) coupled conceptual models with two different machine learning algorithms to improve the results of the conceptual models. Due to their diversity, catchments in Switzerland pose a challenge to models, resulting in variable performance depending on the dominant process considered in the model. The main discharge-generating characteristics include glaciated high mountain catchments, snow-dominated alpine catchments, highly karstified catchments and rainfall dominated lowland catchments.

This study aims to fill this research gap at least partially by comparing six machine learning algorithms (XGBoost, LightGBM, SVM, MLP, LSTM, GRU) with the process-oriented hydrological model "Precipitation-Runoff-Evapotranspiration HRU Model PREVAH" (Viviroli et al., 2009) and assessing their potential in modelling discharge in Swiss catchments.

2. Objective and Research Questions

This study aims to develop recommendations for the usage of machine learning models in the field of rainfall-runoff modelling as well as offering a reflection on possible influences of catchment characteristics and different calibration periods on model performance. The basis of the recommendations is the comparison of the performance of the rainfall-runoff model PREVAH with six different machine learning algorithms. Therefore, the following research questions will be answered:

1. How do the six machine learning algorithms XGBoost, LightGBM, SVM, MLP, LSTM, and GRU perform compared to the conceptual model PREVAH in Muelchi et al. (2020) in the catchments Emme, Plessur, Rosegbach, Venoge, Kander, Verzasca, Ticino, Broye, and Thur?
2. How do different catchment characteristics influence the performance of the machine learning algorithms in selected Swiss catchments?
3. What is the influence of different calibration period lengths on the performance of the machine learning models?

3. Theoretical Background

This section starts by introducing machine learning and the selected machine learning algorithms. It continues with information on different hyperparameter optimisation methods and closes with a description of the frequently used activation functions in machine learning models.

3.1. The History of Machine Learning

Machine learning (ML), an umbrella term for a wide range of computational methods, has its roots in the mid-20th century. In its modern sense, it was first introduced by the psychologist Frank Rosenblatt in 1957. He and his group built a machine called "perceptron" to recognise letters, based on the idea of how nervous systems work (Fradkov, 2020). A big step towards modern algorithms was the invention of backpropagation in the mid-1980s. Using the chain rule, the derivative of the loss function for all internal parameters is calculated. With a method called gradient descent, the internal parameters are then updated to minimize the loss function (Fradkov, 2020). The next major breakthrough came in 1995 when Cortes & Vapnik introduced a version of the support vector machine algorithm for the general non-separable case (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995).

Fradkov (2020) identified three synergistic trends that have led to the success story of ML in the 21st century. The first is big data. The amount of data became so large that new ways of analysing it became necessary. The second was the cost reduction of parallel computing. And finally, the third trend was the proliferation of new algorithms. As a result, ML has found applications in a wide range of fields, such as healthcare, natural language processing, advertising, and finance, to name just a few. Machine learning is increasingly becoming an important tool for businesses and researchers (Çelik, 2018) and finds more and more use in many people's daily life (e.g. ChatGPT).

3.2. What is Machine Learning

Machine Learning (ML) is a new kind of computational algorithm that is designed to "learn" from the data. Traditional algorithms take an input and perform a defined set of actions to produce an output. In opposition to a traditional algorithm a ML algorithm performs a computational process without having every step of the process coded beforehand (i.e. "hard coded"). These algorithms are coded in a way so they can automatically adapt through repetition to produce the best possible output. This process of repetition and adaptation is called training and is technically an automated calibration. For the training, a set of input data (e.g. rainfall, temperature, and catchment size), as well as the desired output (the effectively measured discharge), need to be provided. Based on the input data the algorithm optimises itself to predict the discharge from data on which the model was not trained (El Naqa and Murphy, 2015).

Machine learning algorithms adjust internal parameters to achieve the desired result. They improve on their own errors and try to minimise the number of errors they make (Alzubi et al., 2018). More specifically, they build mathematical models based on so-called training data to make predictions or decisions without being specifically programmed to do so (Bishop, 2006 in Khanzode & Sarode, 2020).

3.3. Advantages and Disadvantages of Machine Learning

One advantage of machine learning algorithms is their ability to handle massive amounts of data. They can analyse datasets which are too large for humans to easily make meaningful predictions (Alzubi et al., 2018). To apply machine learning, it is not necessary to understand how the predictor relates to the

target. Khanzode & Sarode (2020) also mention the often good performance in highly repetitive tasks, as well as the fact that their decision is not biased by emotions.

While it is true that the algorithm itself is not biased by emotion, this leads us to the problem of having biased data to train it on. It is often difficult to create unbiased models because a model is only as good as the data it is trained on. Often, prejudices or, for historical reasons, unbalanced datasets can lead to unintentional biases that may discriminate certain groups (Barocas & Selbst, 2016). It is therefore important to establish best practice rules to avoid the reproduction of historically intentional discrimination when working with personal data (Veale & Binns, 2017). Machine learning algorithms often require large amounts of data to make accurate predictions. As much data is not openly available, this creates a very uneven playing field explaining why big tech companies are leading in this area (Alzubi et al., 2018). Another drawback is the high demand for computing power and thus energy consumption. So far, the development of machine learning algorithms has been based on accuracy rather than efficiency. Although there are some developments in this direction (e.g., the Low Power Image Recognition Challenge (LPIRC)), efficiency is not yet a main goal (García-Martín et al., 2019).

3.4. Machine Learning Algorithms

In this section, the theoretical background of the ML algorithms used in this study is briefly explained and their main benefits and drawbacks are outlined.

3.4.1. XGBoost

The open-source software library originated from a research project at the University of Washington (Chen & Guestrin, 2016) and is developed by an active group of community members (<https://github.com/dmlc/xgboost>). It is available in six programming languages and is compatible with all major platforms.

XGBoost stands for “extreme gradient boosting” and is a regression forest-based gradient boosting algorithm that can handle large datasets very efficiently. It uses gradient boost on the loss function to determine the best data split during tree building (Chen & Guestrin, 2016). The bias after building and applying a tree is the basis for building the next tree until the previously set maximum number of trees is reached. In simple terms, each tree corrects the error of the previous tree. Figure 1 shows a schematic overview of the general architecture. It can handle sparse (incomplete) data and has several features that make this algorithm very efficient with large amounts of data (Chen & Guestrin, 2016). These features include ones that optimise on the statistical side, such as the approximate greedy algorithm, parallel learning, and weighted quantile sketch, as well as implementations which affect hardware usage, such as cache-aware access and blocks for out-of-core computation (Chen & Guestrin, 2016).

Figure 1: Schematic figure of the general architecture of XGBoost (Wang et al., 2019)

The main advantages of XGBoost are its ease of use and its resource efficiency. The low entry barrier opens it up to a wider range of users than more complicated neural network-based models, and its resource efficiency makes hyperparameter optimisation fast, even on large datasets. Another major advantage is the ability to interpret tree-based models. Approaches from game theory can be used to calculate the contribution of predictors to the model output (Lundberg & Lee, 2017; Wang et al., 2022). The main drawback of tree-based algorithms is the limited range of predictable values which is restricted to the range of values already contained in the training set. This is a major limitation when predicting extreme events with a low probability of occurrence, especially if there is a long-term trend. XGBoost has been used to some extent in RRM (Szczechpanek, 2022; Wang et al., 2022, Kumar et al., 2021), but is not as popular as other machine learning models.

3.4.2. LightGBM

LightGBM, short for “light gradient-boosting machine”, was developed by a Microsoft research group and is available as an open-source library (<https://github.com/microsoft/LightGBM>). It is available in several programming languages and runs on all major platforms.

Like XGBoost, LightGBM is a regression forest-based gradient-boosting algorithm (Ke et al., 2017). The two algorithms are closely related but have some distinct differences. Most algorithms grow trees level-wise and prune them in one way or another to remove low information gain splits. LightGBM grows trees leaf by leaf, always evaluating where the next best split is. This method gives better results for the same number of leaves (Shi, 2007). Figure 2 shows the leaf-wise tree growth used in LightGBM and the more standard level wise tree growth respectively.

Figure 2: Schematic tree growth with LightGBM (left) versus a level wise tree growth (right) (Wong, 2022)

In LightGBM two new features were implemented to make the model even more efficient with large datasets, gradient-based one-sided sampling (GOSS) and exclusive feature bundling (EFB) (Ke et al., 2017). When assessing the bias to grow new trees, LightGBM groups the data into already well-performing data points and poorly performing data points. To grow a new tree, only the bias of bad-performing data points and a random sample of good-performing data points are used (Ke et al., 2017). GOSS thus saves computational time with minimal loss of model performance. With EFB LightGBM can combine mutually exclusive features (e.g. gender) into a new feature. This reduces the total number of features and with it, computation time (Ke et al. 2017).

Being closely related, it shares the advantages and disadvantages of XGBoost. Despite the good performance, it has seen considerably less use in RRM than XGBoost (Szczepanek, 2022; Cui et al., 2021; Bian et al., 2023).

3.4.3. Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)

Multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) are the most basic and widely used artificial neural network (ANN) (Popescu et al., 2009). ANNs are inspired by neurons in the brain. Neurons have multiple inputs, some of which are stimulatory and some of which are inhibitory. When a certain threshold is reached, the cell fires a signal to all other connected cells. Learning occurs by strengthening or weakening certain input connections (Drew & Monson, 2000). ANNs consist of two basic components: nodes and connections. Nodes are arranged in so-called layers. ANNs typically consist of an input layer where the data is fed, one or more so-called hidden layers where the learning takes place, and an output layer that gives us the values we are looking for (see Figure 4). Each layer consists of one or more nodes (neurons). Each node in a layer is connected to the next layer in some way. In most cases the layers are densely connected, i.e. every node in layer n is connected to every node in layer $n+1$ (Figure 4). However, linearly connected, and other variants also exist (Zou et al., 2009). The number of layers and the number of nodes in each layer, also called topology, strongly affects model accuracy (Probst et al., 2019). These two hyperparameters need to be optimised during the hyper parameter optimisation (HPO).

Figure 3: Overview of a typical topology of a MLP (Pinto, 2011)

The type of ANN defines what the nodes of the hidden layers look like. In MLPs, the nodes consist of a single activation function (Popescu et al., 2009). Activation functions are usually non-linear functions used to transform the input value of a node. An overview of the most commonly used activation functions is given in the corresponding chapter. The links between nodes consist of weights. These weights can flip and stretch the output of a node. This is the part where the "learning" takes place. The weights control how much information is passed along the connections (Popescu et al., 2009). They are adjusted during training. The fitting is done by a process called back-propagation. To initialise the model, all weights are set to a small random number and biased to zero. Then the training data is fed into the model and the loss is calculated. A commonly used loss function is the mean squared error (MSE). Now the derivative of the loss function is formed with respect to each weight and bias. Gradient descent is then used to update the weights and biases step-wise to minimise the loss (Krogh, 2008; Drew & Monson, 2000). Several implementations with small additions to the classical gradient descent have been implemented.

The main advantages of ANNs are their ability to generalise and their ability to capture non-linear trends. However, it is difficult to analyse the model itself to see how the result is generated. Additionally, the training of an MLP model is computationally much more expensive than the previous methods. Thus, hyperparameter optimisation can be time-consuming (and costly) which requires the use of an efficient optimisation method. Like SVR, MLPs have seen a wide range of applications in RRM (Senthil Kumar, 2005; Sing et al., 2016; Anctil et al., 2004, Modarres, 2009).

3.4.4. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

The LSTM developed by Hochreiter & Schmidhuber (1997) is a recurrent neural network (RNN). RNNs are designed to handle time series like data. Traditional RNNs have a self-connected feedback loop that feeds part of the output back into the node along with the input of the next time step (Zargar, 2021). When using long sequences, they face the problem that the long-term gradient (feedback loop) tends to zero or infinity. If the weight on the feedback loop is less than 1, the long-term gradient vanishes. If the weight is greater than 1, the long-term gradient explodes (Sherstinsky, 2020). LSTMs solve the exploding/vanishing gradient problem by introducing a long-term memory and a short-term memory (self-connected feedback loops) and three so-called gates, which control how much is

remembered from the previous time step and how much is stored in memory for the next time step (Sherstinsky, 2020).

Figure 4: Schematic overview of a LSTM cell (Rahman & Siddiqui, 2019)

Figure 5 shows the structure of an LSTM node, also called a cell. The top horizontal pipeline is the long-term memory, called the cell state. The lower horizontal pipeline is called the hidden state and represents the short-term memory. It is the output of the previous time step. The forget gate takes the hidden state and the input of this time step and determines how much of the cell state (long-term memory) is kept. Then the input gate takes the same inputs and determines how much this time step contributes to the cell state. Finally, the output gate again takes the hidden state and the new input and, together with the cell state, calculates the output of this time step and therefore the hidden state of the next time step. All gates have trainable weights. This makes LSTMs much more computationally expensive than classical neural networks.

LSTMs are designed for classification and prediction based on sequential data and have been used in areas such as speech recognition (Mohamed et al., 2015), translation (Tiwari et al., 2020), robot control (Park et al., 2018), and time series prediction. As they are designed to process time series type data, they have been widely used in the context of RRM (Kratzert et al., 2018; Xiang et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2018; Lees et al., 2021). The disadvantage of LSTMs is the computational power required to train the model, which makes hyperparameter optimisation more costly.

3.4.5. Gated Recurrent Units (GRU)

GRUs, proposed by Cho et al. (2014), are closely related to LSTMs. They also belong to the RNNs and have structures to solve the vanishing/exploding gradient problem that classical RNNs suffer from. Figure 6 shows the structure of a GRU cell. Unlike an LSTM cell, the GRU cell has no cell state. All information is passed through the hidden state. It consists of two gates that control how much information is stored and passed on. A GRU cell has fewer trainable weights and is therefore computationally cheaper than a LSTM cell.

Figure 5: Schematic overview of a GRU cell (Huang et al., 2019)

First, the hidden state of the previous time step and the input of this time step are used to determine what proportion of the previous hidden state is used in the calculation for this time step. This is called the reset gate (r_t). The hidden state of the previous time step and the input of this time step are then used to control which information of the previous hidden state should be forgotten and which new information should be added. This mechanism is also called the update gate (z_t). The output of the reset gate and the input of this time step are then used to calculate the potential hidden state (\tilde{h}_t). The output of the update gate determines the portion of the potential hidden state that is added to the remaining portion of the previous hidden state resulting in the new hidden state.

Like LSTMs, GRUs are designed for classification and prediction based on sequential data. Although used for RRM (Gao et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021; Yokoo et al., 2021), GRUs are not as popular as LSTMs, despite the similarities.

3.4.6. Support Vector Regression (SVR)

Support vector regression (SVR) is a generalised form of support vector machine (SVM) (Awad et al., 2015). SVMs are designed for multivariate binary classification (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995). They define classification as a convex optimisation problem (Awad et al., 2015). The optimisation finds the maximum margins of a hyperplane that splits the data as well as possible while still allowing for misclassification (e.g. outlier, edge cases or not completely separable classes). In SVMs, the margins are expressed as support vectors (Awad et al., 2015). SVR performs regression by finding the simplest non-linear tube with $r = \epsilon$, with ϵ being a defined tolerance level, that contains as many data points as possible while minimizing the distance from the tube to the points outside the tolerance level (Vapnik 1998, 55ff).

Figure 6: Schematic representation of support vector regression (Pasolli et al., 2011)

The advantages of SVR are the lower amount of data required to yield good model results and the high generalization capabilities (Liu et al., 2020). A disadvantage is a noticeable performance loss for larger datasets. SVR is more popular than the tree-based algorithms and has been widely used in RRM outside Switzerland (Botsis et al., 2011; Chiang et al., 2022, Granata et al., 2016).

3.5. Hyperparameter Optimisation

In machine learning models two types of parameters exist. Firstly, the “model parameters” which can be initialized and updated through the data learning process. And secondly, the “hyperparameters” (HPs). Hyperparameters are parameters that are not learned from the data but are set before training a ML model. HPs define the model architecture and control various aspects of the learning process, such as the complexity of the model or the speed at which it learns (Yang and Shami, 2020). There are different types of HPs: categorical, discrete, and continuous HPs (Decastro-García et al., 2019).

The process of finding the model architecture best suited for the problem with the optimal hyperparameter configuration is called hyperparameter optimisation (HPO), also known as hyperparameter tuning (Yang and Shami, 2020). Due to the important role of HPs, the process of HPO is considered one of the most important steps in configuring a machine learning model. Some argue that it is even more important than the type of model used (Szczepanek, 2022). This is because, when applied to the same model and data, different sets of hyperparameters can produce very different results. Therefore, finding the optimal set of hyperparameters can significantly improve the performance of a machine learning model (Probst et al., 2019; Claesen & De Moor, 2015).

Many different types of optimisation techniques have emerged over the years, with different strengths and drawbacks. In the following subsections, the most important ones are briefly explained.

3.5.1. Manual Experience Based Optimisation

The most low-tech version of HP optimisation is manual optimisation, based on experience. For this method a profound understanding of the used ML algorithm and its hyperparameter value settings is needed (Yang and Shami, 2020). While this method can be used for models with very few HPs it becomes almost impossible within a reasonable time for more complex models. We believe it is better practice to use experience to constrain the search space of the hyperparameters using one of the techniques mentioned below.

3.5.2. Grid Search Optimisation

Grid search is a commonly used optimisation method. It is based on the permutation of a defined set of parameter values (Yang & Shami, 2020). This spans a finite n-dimensional search space, with n being the number of hyperparameters. This method can get quite resource-intensive because the number of combinations grows exponentially as the number of parameters increases. One way of optimising would be to first evaluate over a coarse selection of parameter values and then perform a finer optimisation around the best combinations in a second step. In a case with few well-constrained hyperparameters, grid search may still be a viable option (Yang & Shami, 2020).

3.5.3. Random Search Optimisation

Random search works similarly to grid search. The difference is that instead of a predefined set of parameter values random sets are tested. Bergstra & Bengio (2012) have shown that random search leads to an equally good or even better parameter set in less time than grid search. While this method is more efficient than grid search, there is no way to directly exploit previously well-performing regions.

3.5.4. Gradient-Based Optimisation

Gradient descent takes a randomly chosen parameter set and calculates the gradient to choose the direction to move to a better parameter set until a local optimum is reached (Bengio, 2000). This poses potential issues as the global and the local optimum are identical for convex functions only (Yang & Shami, 2020). In addition, it suffers from the same problems of complexity as the grid search optimisation.

3.5.5. Bayesian Parameter Optimisation

Like the gradient-based optimisation, the Bayesian optimisation is an iterative algorithm. This allows the selection of a new parameter set based on previous results (Snoek et al., 2012). Bayesian optimisation is made up of two main components: a probabilistic surrogate model modelling the performance of different parameter combinations, and an acquisition function selecting the next parameter set to test based on the surrogate model (Yang & Shami, 2020). The acquisition function manages a trade-off between exploring new areas and continuing to investigate promising areas. There are several different surrogate models. The most commonly used include the Gaussian process (Seeger, 2004), random forest (also called SMAC) (Hutter et al., 2010), and tree-structured Parzen estimator (Bergstra et al., 2011). It has been shown that near-optimal parameter sets can be found within a few steps (Snoek et al., 2012).

3.5.6. Multi Fidelity Optimisation

Training a model can take a considerable amount of time. Training times of minutes can be considered fast. Complex models with large datasets can take several hours to days for a single training run (Claesen & De Moor, 2015). This means that each optimisation iteration is costly. The multi-fidelity approach first optimises on a subset of the training data to explore promising regions. In a second step, the entire training data is used to optimise the entire model (Bottou, 2010). This way, poorly performing parameter sets can be discarded before costly training with the full dataset (Yang & Shami, 2020).

3.5.7. Meta Heuristic Optimisation

Metaheuristic algorithms are inspired by biological theories as for example evolution and are widely used for optimisations. Like in Bayesian parameter optimisation they do not rely on extensive search but rather adapt on the results of previous iterations. They can escape local maxima and can be used to solve non-convex, non-continuous, and non-smooth optimisation problems (Yang & Shami, 2020).

3.6. Activation Functions

In this chapter, the most commonly used activation functions are explained. Activation functions are used in nodes to transform the input. They come in different forms, each with their own advantages and disadvantages. Explaining all activation functions would go beyond the scope of this thesis. Therefore, the focus is on the basic forms and those used in this study.

3.6.1. Sigmoid

The sigmoid function $f(x)=1/(1+e^{-x})$ returns values between 0 and 1. The sigmoid function was mainly used in the early days of neural networks because it suffers from the vanishing gradient problem for higher and lower inputs (Dubey et al., 2022). It was the activation function of choice for binary classification problems (Marcu & Grava, 2021).

Figure 7: Sigmoid activation function

3.6.2. Hyperbolic Tangent (Tan-h)

The hyperbolic tangent function $f(x)=(e^x-e^{-x})/(e^x+e^{-x})$ is similar to the sigmoid function. It returns values between -1 and 1. It has a stronger gradient than the sigmoid function, but it also suffers from the vanishing gradient problem for input values far from zero (Marcu & Grava, 2021).

Figure 8: Hyperbolic Tangent (*tan-h*) activation function

3.6.3. Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU)

This simple function of the form $f(x)=\max(0,x)$ has many variations (Dubey et al., 2022). The ReLU function has two main advantages. First, it solves the vanishing gradient problem of the two functions mentioned above. And second, it is faster to compute (Marcu & Grava, 2021). However, the ReLU's non-use of negative values can create 'dead' neurons with mostly negative input values (Marcu & Grava, 2021).

Figure 9: Rectified linear unit (*ReLU*) activation function

3.6.4. Softplus

The softplus function $f(x)=\ln(ex+1)$ (Dougas et al., 2000) approximates the ReLU function. It solves the problem of ignoring negative input values (Marcu & Grava, 2021). Continuous differentiability is ensured by the smooth shape (Dubey et al., 2022).

Figure 10: Softplus activation function

3.7. The Conceptual Model PREVAH

The PREVAH model (Precipitation-Runoff-Evapotranspiration HRU Model PREVAH) is a spatially explicit, process-oriented model designed to model catchments with complex topography (Muelchi et al., 2020). The model core has been in existence for about 25 years (Gurtz et al., 1999) and has been complemented by several tools. The tools simplify tasks around the models, as for example data pre-processing, model parameterisation or visualisation of results (Viviroli et al., 2009). The general discharge generation submodule is inspired by the HBV model but has been modified to a semi-distributed model and offers many improvements over the original HBV model (Gurtz et al., 1999). The catchment is divided into so-called hydrological response units (HRU), areas with similar responses. For each HRU a storage cascade is simulated and then combined into an area mean. Figure 11 shows the storage cascade used in the model. The model is designed for small mountainous catchments and consists of several sub-modules. Internally, the model always runs with hourly time steps. Advantages described by Viviroli et al. (2009) are the ease of use due to the graphical interface and the flexibility with respect to data requirements due to the possibility to use more or less complex submodules. Limitations include catchment sizes below 10 km² and above 1000 km², and arid or semi-arid regions for which no specific process description is implemented. This model was used by Muelchi et al. (2020), whose results were used as a benchmark for this study.

Figure 11: Storage cascade of the conceptual model PREVAH (Viviroli et al., 2009)

4. Methods and Data

This section provides an in-depth description of the methods applied in this study. First, the catchment selection is described, followed by the data and preprocessing used to conduct this study. Afterwards, the methods used for modelling and model comparison are described in detail. All calculations were done in R. The R source code is available on GitHub (see Annex).

4.1. Research Area

All nine catchments used in this study were used by Muelchi et al. (2020), whose PREVAH models are used as a benchmark for comparison. Muelchi et al. (2020) defined six representative catchments (Rosegbach, Kander, Plessur, Emme, Venoge, and Verzasca) where the PREVAH model performed well. These catchments cover a wide range of catchment characteristics and are unregulated. In addition, the catchments Thur, Broye, and Ticino were selected. An overview of where these catchments are located is shown in Figure 12. Table 1 summarizes the most important catchment characteristics. This selection encompasses a broad spectrum of catchment characteristics and model performance from the benchmark model, providing an in-depth understanding of the strengths and limitations of the ML models compared to the conceptual model.

Figure 12: Overview of the selected catchments and their location

Table 1: Characteristics of the catchments used in this study

Catchment	MQ (m ³ /s)	Station elevation (m.a.s.l.)	Catchment area (km ²)	Mean elevation (m.a.s.l.)	Regime Type
Rosegbach – Pontresina*	2.8	1770	66	2704	Glazial (21.7)
Kander – Hondrich*	20.0	650	491	1854	Nivo-Glazial (5.1)
Plessur – Chur*	8.0	565	264	1868	Nival
Emme - Emmenmatt	12.0	641	443	1065	Nivo-Pluvial
Venoge - Ecublens	4.1	384	228	686	Pluvial
Verzasca - Lavertezzo	11.0	495	185	1651	Nivo Pluvial south alpine
Thur - Andelfingen	47.0	361	1702	770	Pluvial
Broye - Payerne	7.7	446	416	715	Pluvial inférieure
Ticino - Bellinzona	68.0	224	1517	1679	Nivo Pluvial south alpine

* These catchments are dominated by meltwater; the others are mainly influenced by rainfall.

4.2. Data

In this study, the input variables daily mean temperature and daily precipitation sum were used to simulate the daily mean discharge. All data used for modelling were taken from the CAMELS_CH hydro-meteorological data set compiled by Höge et al. (2023). The shapefiles used to create the overview of the catchment locations are openly available on the website of FOEN (catchments and gauging stations) and SwissTopo (boarders, rivers, lakes).

4.3. Data Preparation

To provide the models with information about past conditions, several lagged, rolling mean and summed time series were derived from the original data (Table 2). Additionally, for all neural network-based models the data was normalized to ensure that all input features are on the same scale. This leads to a faster and more accurate convergence (Singh & Singh, 2020) as otherwise larger input numbers have inherently more importance. Singh & Singh (2020) showed that the type of normalization showing the best modelling results depends on the dataset. In this study, a z-normalization was used to centre them around zero with a standard deviation of one. Preliminary testing showed better results (more stable and accurate) with z-normalization than min-max-normalization often used in ML which scales the data between zero and one.

Table 2: Derived variables used for modelling

Air Temperature	Daily Precipitation Sum
Lag (1-7)	Lag (1-7)
Mean (3,5,7,15,30,60)	Sum (1-7, 15, 30)
Lag 30 of mean 30	Lag 30 of sum 30

To better predict high discharge events with low reoccurrence the top two percent of the discharge measurements in the training period were duplicated two times. Preliminary testing showed that the tripling of flood occurrences enables the models to better predict these rare events. As a side effect, some models started to overestimate discharges in the lower range. Duplicating the lowest two percent of the data counteracted this effect effectively.

4.4. Machine Learning Algorithms: Technical Parameters

In the following sections the technical parameters of the ML algorithms and their HPO is described in detail.

4.4.1. XGBoost

The XGBoost model were built with the R package “xgboost” (v. 1.7.5.1). XGBoost has many hyperparameters that can be adjusted. In this study the six HPs in Table 3 have been optimised. The hyperparameter optimisation was achieved through a Bayesian optimisation process, paired with a five-fold cross-validation. The optimisation range was established based on preliminary testing. Additionally, if a model's optimised hyperparameter set was found to contain a value that was approaching a range limit, the limit was extended. However, this does not apply to the “nrounds” parameter, as even though some models exhibit a slightly improved RMSE with higher values, the actual gain in model performance is negligible. Each catchment's specific set of hyperparameters can be found in Annex A.

Table 3: Optimised Hyperparameters for XGBoost

Hyperparameter	Description	Optimisation range
eta	Eta is the learning rate and controls how much is learned per round. High values lead to fast overfitting	0.001 – 0.25
max depth	Maximum depth of a tree. Larger tree depths allow to learn more complex data structures and more different output values but lead to overfitting.	2 – 12
Min child weight	Controls how much weight a branch must have to be further partitioned. Higher numbers lead to more conservative trees.	1-50
alpha	L1 regularisation on weights	1 – 12
lambda	L2 regularisation on weights	1 – 12
nrounds	maximum number of boosting iterations	1 – 250

4.4.2. LightGBM

The LightGBM models were constructed with the R package “lightgbm” (v. 3.3.5). LightGBM has numerous hyperparameters that can be adjusted. In this study, the five HPs in Table 4, have been optimised. This selection is according to the developer’s recommendation.

The hyperparameter optimisation was achieved through a Bayesian optimisation process, paired with a five-fold cross-validation. The optimisation range was established based on preliminary testing. Additionally, if a model's optimised hyperparameter set was found to contain a value that was approaching a range limit, the limit was extended. However, as for XGBoost, this does not apply to the “nrounds” parameter, as even though some models exhibit a slightly improved RMSE with higher

values, the actual gain in model performance is negligible. Each catchment's specific set of hyperparameters can be found in Annex A.

Table 4: Optimised Hyperparameters for LightGBM

Hyperparameter	Description	Optimisation range
eta	Eta is the learning rate and controls how much is learned per round. High values lead to fast overfitting	0.001 – 0.25
max depth	Maximum depth of a tree. Larger tree depths allow the model to learn more complex data structures and more different output values but lead to overfitting.	2 – 15
num_leaves	Controls the maximum number of nodes per tree. Higher numbers can lead to overfitting.	1 – 150
min_data_in_leaf	Controls the minimum number of data points in each leaf. Used to decrease overfitting	5 – 50
nrounds	maximum number of boosting iterations	1 – 200

4.4.3. Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)

The MLP models were built using the R package “keras” (v. 2.13.0). The following rules concerning the topology have been followed while designing the models:

- All layers have the same number of nodes.
- Between two layers there is always a dropout layer to prevent overfitting.
- The output layer contains one densely connected node without activation function.

The five HPs shown in Table 5 were optimised. The hyperparameter optimisation was achieved through a Bayesian optimisation process. As cross-validation is not viable due to the time needed to complete the training, in each epoch 17% of the training data, randomly chosen, were excluded from the training process and used as validation. The optimisation ranges were established based on preliminary testing. Additionally, if a model's optimised hyperparameter set was found to contain a value that was approaching a range limit, the limit was extended. However, it should be noted that this does not hold true for the nlayers parameter. The gain in actual model performance beyond 4 layers is insignificant, but the additional model complexity prolongs the training time considerably. 200 epochs were used to train the models with an early stopping constraint of 10 epochs without performance gain. The loss function “mse” (mean squared error) and optimiser “adam” were utilised. The “softplus” activation function has proven to be superior to “ReLU” in preliminary testing in both, training times and model performance. Each catchment's specific set of hyperparameters can be found in Annex A.

Table 5: Optimised Hyperparameters for MLP

Hyperparameter	Description	Optimisation range
nlayers	Number of layers in the neural network	1 – 4
nnodes	Number of nodes in each layer	5 – 150
dropout rate	Percentage of inputs randomly set to 0 during training to prevent overfitting	0 – 0.4
batch size	Step size after which the weights are updated within an epoch	5 – 150
Learning rate	Higher learning rates lead to faster convergence but might be unstable	0.001 – 0.015

4.4.4. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

The LSTM models were built using the R package “keras” (v. 2.13.0). The following rules concerning the topology have been followed while designing the models:

- All layers have the same number of nodes.
- Between two LSTM layers there is always a dropout layer to prevent overfitting.
- The output layer contains one densely connected node without activation function.

LSTMs have many hyperparameters that can be adjusted. In this study, the LSTM models have been optimised for the six HPs shown in Table 6.

The hyperparameter optimisation was achieved through a Bayesian optimisation process. As cross-validation is not viable due to the time needed to complete the training, in each epoch 17% of the training data, randomly chosen, were excluded from the training process and used as validation. The optimisation range was established based on preliminary testing. Additionally, if a model's optimised hyperparameter set was found to contain a value that was approaching a range limit, the limit was extended. However, it should be noted that this does not hold true for the nlayers parameter. The gain in actual model performance beyond 4 layers is insignificant, but the additional model complexity prolongs the training time considerably. 200 epochs were used to train the models with an early stopping constraint of 10 epochs without performance gain. The loss function “mse” (mean squared error) and optimiser “adam” were utilised. Each catchment's specific set of hyperparameters can be found in Annex A.

Table 6: Optimised Hyperparameters for LSTM

Hyperparameter	Description	Optimisation range
nlayers	Number of layers in the neural network	1 – 4
nnodes	Number of nodes in each layer	5 – 150
Dropout rate	Percentage of inputs randomly set to 0 during training to prevent overfitting	0 – 0.4
batch size	Step size after which the weights are updated within an epoch	5 – 150
Learning Rate	Higher learning rates lead to faster convergence but might be unstable	0.001 – 0.015
step size	Number of time steps of the input data	5 – 100

4.4.5. Gated Recurrent Units (GRU)

The GRU models were built using the R package “keras” (v. 2.13.0). The following rules concerning the topology have been followed while designing the models:

- All layers have the same number of nodes.
- Between two GRU layers there is always a dropout layer to prevent overfitting.
- The output layer contains one densely connected node without activation function.

GRUs have many hyperparameters that can be adjusted. In this study, the models have been optimised for the six HPs shown in Table 7.

The HPO of GRU-based models were done identically to those based on LSTM (see 4.4.4).

Table 7: Optimised Hyperparameters for GRU

Hyperparameter	Description	Optimisation range
nlayers	Number of layers in the neural network	1 – 4
nnodes	Number of nodes in each layer	5 – 150
Dropout Rate	Percentage of inputs randomly set to 0 during training to prevent overfitting	0 – 0.4
Batch Size	Step size after which the weights are updated within an epoch	5 – 150
Learning Rate	Higher learning rates lead to faster convergence but might be unstable	0.001 – 0.015
Step Size	Number of time steps of the input data	5 – 100

4.4.6. Support Vector Regression (SVR)

The SVR models were constructed using the “e1071” package in R (v. 1.7-13). The default variant, epsilon-regression, was used. The epsilon-regression offers two hyperparameters for optimisation.

The hyperparameter optimisation was performed using a Bayesian optimisation process. The optimisation range (see Table 8) was established based on preliminary testing. Each catchment's specific set of hyperparameters can be found in Annex A.

Table 8: Optimised Hyperparameters for SVR

Hyperparameter	Description	Optimisation range
epsilon	Size of the epsilon tube.	0.005 – 0.6
cost	Cost of constraint violation used in the regularization	1 – 25

4.5. Hyperparameter Optimisation

As mentioned in the previous section all hyperparameter optimisation was performed using the Bayesian approach. A Gaussian surrogate model was used, as this was directly available with the R package "ParBayesianOptimisation" (v. 1.2.6). The function has many parameters to optimise the performance for example the number of initial points, the parameter values of the initial points, the number of optimisation steps after the initial points and parameters affecting the exploration/exploitation behaviour of the optimisation. Only the number of initial points as well as the number of optimisation steps have been adjusted. For all other parameters, the default values provided by the authors were used. The number of initial points and optimisation steps used for each ML algorithm are listed in Table 9. More complex models have more initial steps to better cover the possible combinations of HP values. During preliminary testing, it appeared that the Gaussian surrogate model struggled with efficiently optimising the HPs of the NN-based models. Therefore, the initial points were increased despite the computational cost connected to them.

Table 9: Adjusted parameters used for hyperparameter optimisation

ML Algorithm	Initial Points	Optimisation Steps
XGBoost	25	15
LightGBM	20	15
MLP	30	15
LSTM	30	15
GRU	30	15
SVR	20	10

4.6. Model Calibration and Validation

Two different calibration–validation splits were used in this study. One is the same as Muelchi et al. (2020) used in their study. This ensures that differences in the compared model performances can be attributed to the models themselves and are not affected by differences in the validation period. The models were calibrated and validated with data from 1984 to 2015 with an exception for Verzasca where data availability started in 1990. Model calibration has been performed on even years, model validation on odd years. This pattern should minimise the influence of random and non-random trends on model calibration. In addition, the models were calibrated and validated over a longer time period (1981 – 2020) to see if the models improve with more calibration data. Additionally, only every third year was used for validation to increase the training data even further. This resulted in a calibration length of 16 years and 28 years respectively.

4.7. Model Comparison

In order to be able to compare the results to Muelchi et al. (2020) the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (Nash & Sutcliffe, 1970) and Kling-Gupta efficiency (Gupta et al., 2009) were used to analyse model performance. Both performance indicators measure model accuracy, where 1 describes a perfect model. The Kling-Gupta efficiency focuses more on the correct variability and correlation of the discharge. Additionally, the Pearson correlation coefficient and RMSE are calculated to be able to compare the results to more literature besides Muelchi et al. (2020).

4.7.1. Nash-Sutcliffe-Efficiency (NSE)

The Nash-Sutcliffe-Efficiency (NSE) (Nash & Sutcliffe, 1970) is a metric commonly used in hydrology to evaluate model performance. It compares the mean squared error (MSE) of the model with the MSE that would result from using the mean discharge as a predictor. Therefore, an NSE of 0 indicates that the model has the MSE as if mean discharge had been used as the model. An NSE of 1 indicates a perfect fit between the model and the observation.

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T (Q_o^t - Q_m^t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^T (Q_o^t - \bar{Q}_o)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where Q_o corresponds to the observation and Q_m to the modelled value.

4.7.2. Kling-Gupta-Efficiency (KGE)

The Kling-Gupta-Efficiency was introduced by Kling & Gupta (2009) as an alternative to the NSE. They showed that the NSE, when used as a model calibration criterion, leads to an underestimation of variability and therefore to an underestimation of discharge. They proposed a new criterion, the KGE which focuses more on the variability and overcomes this problem. Unlike the NSE, the KGE is not directly compared to a benchmark, and a KGE of 0 has no real meaning. Koben et al. (2019) showed that the benchmark of mean discharge results in a KGE of $1 - \sqrt{2} = -0.41$. Like the NSE, a KGE of 1 indicates a perfect fit.

$$KGE = 1 - \sqrt{(r - 1)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_o} - 1\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\mu_s}{\mu_o} - 1\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

Where σ_o corresponds to the standard deviation of the observations, σ_m corresponds to the standard deviation of the modelled values, μ_o to the mean of the observations, μ_m to the mean of the modelled values, and r to the Pearson Correlation Coefficient.

4.7.3. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC)

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) is a measure for the linear relationships between two variables. It is calculated by building the covariance and dividing it by the product of the standard deviations. It ranges between -1 and 1, with -1 describing a data distribution on a line with a negative slope and 1 describing a data distribution on a line with a positive slope. A perfect model hitting all the measured data would have a PCC of 1.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (3)$$

4.7.4. Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)

The Root Mean Squared Error is a widely used performance measure. It ranges from zero to positive infinity, with lower values indicating better model performance. Because the residuals are squared

bigger residuals have more weight. A disadvantage of this performance metric is that it is scale dependent. This makes comparisons between different catchments meaningless.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Q_m - Q_o)^2} \quad (4)$$

Where Q_o corresponds to the observation and Q_m to the modelled value.

Normalising to the long-term mean can overcome the problem of scale dependence of the RMSE when comparing different catchments. One solution is to normalize the RMSE with the long-term mean. This allows for a more comprehensive comparison of model performance across catchments with different amount of discharge.

$$NRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Q_m - Q_o)^2}}{MQ_o} \quad (5)$$

Where Q_o corresponds to the observation, Q_m to the modelled value, and MQ_o to the mean observation.

4.7.5. Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

Like the RMSE the MAE is a widely used performance measure. It also ranges from zero to positive infinity. Lower values indicate better model performance. It is as well dependant on the scale of the variables.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n |Q_m - Q_o| \quad (6)$$

Where Q_o corresponds to the observation and Q_m to the modelled value.

Like the RMSE the MAE can be normalised with the long term mean to remove the scale dependency.

$$NMAE = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n |Q_m - Q_o|}{MQ_o} \quad (7)$$

Where Q_o corresponds to the observation, Q_m to the modelled value, and MQ_o to the mean observation.

5. Results

In this section, the results are presented. First, the performance metrics, consisting of the general performance metrics and volumetric performance metrics, are presented followed by the hydrographs of the models, both sorted by catchment. The hydrograph section starts with the regime plots (Figures 12 to 29) to visualize the model's capabilities to reproduce seasonal characteristics. The regime plots are followed by time series plots of monthly mean values (Figures 30 to 47). All results are presented for both calibration/validation splits used in the study.

5.1. Performance Metrics

The results of the performance metrics are presented by catchment in Tables 13 to 48 below. For each catchment, the first two tables show the general model performance metrics, while the third and fourth tables show the volumetric performance. The first and the third table always correspond to the calibration period used by Muelchi et al. (2020), the second and fourth table corresponds to the extended calibration period. The two best results in the general model performance metrics tables are highlighted in blue, the two worst results are highlighted in red. In the volumetric performance tables, a discharge surplus is highlighted in blue, and a discharge deficit is highlighted in red. The colour intensity depends on the deviation from the measured value.

The results of the tested algorithms reveal great variations in performance across the different models and catchments. Among the algorithms assessed, the regression forest-based algorithms consistently demonstrated strong performance in both rainfall and meltwater-dominated catchments based on RMSE, MAE, and NSE values (Tables 13, 14, 17, 18, 21, 22, 25, 26, 29, 30, 33, 34, 37, 38, 41, 42, 45, and 46). These values were consistently close together for both algorithms. Additionally, also in terms of the KGE metric, these algorithms remain among the top performers. However, it is worth noting that they fall behind the MLP in the rainfall-dominated catchments of Emme, Ticino, and Thur (Table 13, 14, 37, 38, 45, 46). Also, in rainfall-dominated catchments, the KGE of XGBoost tends to be lower than the KGE of LightGBM. This effect is stronger for the shorter calibration period.

The SVR algorithm performs similarly to the regression forest-based algorithms in all performance metrics when trained with the larger dataset with an exception for the KGE which is lower in rainfall-dominated catchments. However, when trained with the smaller dataset, the algorithm does not reach the performance of the regression forest-based algorithms in rainfall-dominated catchments.

The KGE of the MLP-based models shows a big range (0.663 to 0.941). The NSE on the other hand is more consistent (0.691 to 0.882 mostly staying above 0.8). Compared to the other algorithms its performance is in the midrange. The RMSE and MAE generally are slightly worse than the corresponding values of the regression forest-based algorithms.

The RNN-based algorithms perform poorly on all performance metrics except when examining the NSE as well as the KGE of the LSTM in catchments dominated by meltwater, such as Plessur, Rosegbach, and Kander (Tables 10 and 11).

Table 10: Mean NSE and KGE values for rainfall-dominated and meltwater-dominated catchments - short calibration period

	Rain dominated		Melt dominated	
	NSE	KGE	NSE	KGE
XGBoost	0.820	0.735	0.820	0.793
LightGBM	0.824	0.777	0.816	0.795
MLP	0.777	0.800	0.786	0.723
LSTM	0.507	0.504	0.746	0.778
GRU	0.471	0.506	0.725	0.648
SVR	0.766	0.692	0.813	0.795

Table 11: Mean NSE and KGE values for rainfall-dominated and melt-water-dominated catchments - long calibration period

	Rain dominated		Melt dominated	
	NSE	KGE	NSE	KGE
XGBoost	0.839	0.802	0.855	0.807
LightGBM	0.838	0.827	0.856	0.798
MLP	0.816	0.837	0.808	0.73
LSTM	0.515	0.521	0.780	0.747
GRU	0.511	0.480	0.76	0.605
SVR	0.838	0.776	0.851	0.790

In general performance metrics improve with an extended calibration period. This can be seen most clearly with the RMSE on which the models were optimised. To remove the scale dependency of the RMSE and MAE and compare them over all catchments they have been normalized by the mean discharge. The mean NRMSE and NMAE over all catchments can be found in Table 12. All models' average NRMSE and NMAE improve with an extended calibration period. The effect is most prominent for the SVR models and weakest for the LSTM-based ones (Table 12).

Table 12: Mean normalized RMSE and MAE over all catchments for both calibration periods

Model	Short Calibration Period		Long Calibration Period		Absolute Difference	
	NRMSE	NMAE	NRMSE	NMAE	NRMSE	NMAE
XGBoost	0.509	0.259	0.436	0.237	-0.072	-0.022
LightGBM	0.505	0.262	0.438	0.239	-0.066	-0.023
MLP	0.566	0.284	0.484	0.267	-0.082	-0.017
LSTM	0.727	0.357	0.695	0.358	-0.032	0.001
GRU	0.793	0.393	0.705	0.368	-0.088	-0.025
SVR	0.593	0.305	0.443	0.248	-0.150	-0.057

The volumetric model performances, presented in the following section, show whether the models overestimate or underestimate the discharge under the specified flow conditions.

The 99th percentile tends to be underestimated by all algorithms except the MLP which overestimates the 99th percentile in about half of the cases. In most cases, the RNN-based models, especially the GRU-based models, show the greatest underestimation. The regression forest-based algorithms profit greatly from the longer training period whereas the others do not show such a clear picture.

While all algorithms show some cases where the 5th percentile is underestimated it is most prominent with LSTM and SVR models. The overestimation is generally bigger than the underestimation. The length of the calibration period seems to have no clear impact on the accuracy of the 5th percentile.

XGBoost, LightGBM, and SVR generally underestimate the mean discharge, mostly staying within a 3.5% deviation from the measured mean. The neural network-based algorithms on the other hand tend to show a larger deviation from the measured mean in both directions, under and overestimation. Additionally, a bigger proportion of the models overestimate the mean, especially the recurrent network based, where under and overestimations occur equally often.

Emme

Table 13: Performance metrics - Emme - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.82	0.89	-
XGBoost	7.06	3.54	0.774	0.641	0.883
LightGBM	6.51	3.3	0.807	0.695	0.9
MLP	7.91	3.95	0.715	0.742	0.847
LSTM	10.96	5.58	0.454	0.427	0.676
GRU	11.03	5.44	0.447	0.448	0.672
SVR	7.79	3.51	0.724	0.615	0.854

Table 14: Performance metrics - Emme - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	5.83	3.25	0.807	0.781	0.899
LightGBM	5.86	3.27	0.806	0.845	0.898
MLP	7.01	3.67	0.722	0.855	0.862
LSTM	10.1	5.68	0.422	0.564	0.68
GRU	9.78	5.55	0.458	0.459	0.684
SVR	6.17	3.34	0.784	0.702	0.887

Table 15: Volumetric Model Performance - Emme - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	11.77	70.17	1.78
XGBoost	-3.57%	-11.43%	-23.03%
LightGBM	-2.46%	-12.08%	1.69%
MLP	3.57%	3.14%	60.11%
LSTM	-0.42%	-23.64%	-7.30%
GRU	1.44%	-22.73%	-7.30%
SVR	-6.12%	-11.94%	7.87%

Table 16: Volumetric Model Performance - Emme - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	12.06	64.36	1.91
XGBoost	-1.58%	-3.93%	8.90%
LightGBM	-0.41%	-2.61%	15.71%
MLP	4.31%	7.30%	42.41%
LSTM	11.19%	-10.69%	24.08%
GRU	7.63%	-21.21%	56.02%
SVR	-3.48%	-8.19%	15.18%

Plessur

Table 17: Performance metrics - Plessur - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.87	0.9	-
XGBoost	2.95	1.74	0.774	0.789	0.881
LightGBM	3	1.8	0.766	0.799	0.876
MLP	3.45	2.14	0.691	0.751	0.835
LSTM	3.28	1.97	0.721	0.86	0.862
GRU	3.32	2.04	0.715	0.804	0.851
SVR	3.02	1.88	0.763	0.769	0.875

Table 18: Performance metrics - Plessur - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	2.79	1.76	0.794	0.797	0.891
LightGBM	2.81	1.76	0.79	0.767	0.889
MLP	3.05	1.98	0.753	0.68	0.869
LSTM	2.96	1.87	0.768	0.798	0.877
GRU	3.01	1.99	0.759	0.65	0.873
SVR	2.75	1.78	0.799	0.734	0.896

Table 19: Volumetric Model Performance - Plessur - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	5.64	28.4	0.51
XGBoost	-2.66%	-17.61%	29.41%
LightGBM	-1.42%	-17.39%	29.41%
MLP	5.14%	-18.31%	147.06%
LSTM	0.00%	-15.46%	-23.53%
GRU	5.32%	-26.13%	50.98%
SVR	-4.96%	-21.58%	-68.63%

Table 20: Volumetric Model Performance - Plessur - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	5.88	26.3	0.46
XGBoost	-1.36%	-7.15%	56.52%
LightGBM	-1.87%	-11.25%	63.04%
MLP	-3.74%	-29.35%	167.39%
LSTM	0.68%	-9.43%	93.48%
GRU	1.87%	-18.78%	273.91%
SVR	-5.78%	-15.02%	19.57%

Rosegbach

Table 21: Performance metrics - Rosegbach - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.83	0.91	-
XGBoost	1.41	0.69	0.871	0.841	0.933
LightGBM	1.41	0.68	0.873	0.85	0.934
MLP	1.52	0.74	0.851	0.647	0.934
LSTM	1.75	0.84	0.801	0.669	0.901
GRU	2	0.97	0.742	0.462	0.895
SVR	1.46	0.74	0.862	0.857	0.929

Table 22: Performance metrics - Rosegbach - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	1.15	0.62	0.909	0.822	0.955
LightGBM	1.18	0.64	0.905	0.819	0.952
MLP	1.44	0.77	0.857	0.654	0.937
LSTM	1.6	0.83	0.825	0.627	0.919
GRU	1.66	0.9	0.811	0.62	0.909
SVR	1.31	0.74	0.883	0.822	0.94

Table 23: Volumetric Model Performance - Rosegbach - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	2.99	14.48	0.08
XGBoost	-2.01%	-9.05%	12.50%
LightGBM	-1.34%	-8.49%	0.00%
MLP	-12.71%	-22.51%	125.00%
LSTM	-9.70%	-18.23%	-12.50%
GRU	-22.41%	-26.93%	12.50%
SVR	-2.68%	-9.19%	12.50%

Table 24: Volumetric Model Performance - Rosegbach - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	2.88	14.52	0.1
XGBoost	-3.13%	-11.09%	30.00%
LightGBM	-3.13%	-10.33%	20.00%
MLP	-11.81%	-27.82%	160.00%
LSTM	-10.07%	-22.25%	80.00%
GRU	-8.33%	-27.13%	230.00%
SVR	-3.13%	-9.85%	40.00%

Venoge

Table 25: Performance metrics - Venoge - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.89	0.93	-
XGBoost	1.91	1.02	0.842	0.692	0.922
LightGBM	1.87	1.03	0.848	0.777	0.922
MLP	2.04	1.08	0.819	0.903	0.911
LSTM	2.8	1.4	0.66	0.706	0.815
GRU	3.04	1.62	0.599	0.445	0.778
SVR	1.89	1.18	0.846	0.83	0.92

Table 26: Performance metrics - Venoge - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	1.99	1.05	0.86	0.88	0.928
LightGBM	1.94	1.05	0.867	0.856	0.931
MLP	2.18	1.13	0.831	0.852	0.922
LSTM	3.08	1.53	0.664	0.771	0.821
GRU	3.13	1.5	0.654	0.742	0.814
SVR	1.93	1.04	0.868	0.923	0.933

Table 27: Volumetric Model Performance - Venoge - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	3.85	24.62	0.47
XGBoost	-6.49%	-16.29%	14.89%
LightGBM	-5.19%	-7.23%	8.51%
MLP	-3.38%	4.31%	42.55%
LSTM	-1.30%	-9.18%	8.51%
GRU	0.00%	-30.58%	100.00%
SVR	-1.82%	-2.72%	-40.43%

Table 28: Volumetric Model Performance - Venoge - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	4.24	26.65	0.52
XGBoost	1.89%	-2.06%	5.77%
LightGBM	2.36%	-3.23%	-1.92%
MLP	-2.83%	11.67%	-13.46%
LSTM	-1.18%	-1.43%	-55.77%
GRU	-0.24%	2.10%	26.92%
SVR	0.71%	1.35%	9.62%

Kander

Table 29: Performance metrics - Kander - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.87	0.93	-
XGBoost	6.93	4.02	0.815	0.748	0.903
LightGBM	7.02	4.02	0.81	0.736	0.9
MLP	6.91	3.93	0.816	0.77	0.904
LSTM	8.6	4.88	0.715	0.806	0.85
GRU	8.53	4.84	0.719	0.679	0.848
SVR	6.93	3.91	0.815	0.758	0.903

Table 30: Performance metrics - Kander - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	5.72	3.63	0.862	0.801	0.93
LightGBM	5.46	3.46	0.874	0.808	0.937
MLP	6.62	4.15	0.815	0.856	0.91
LSTM	7.77	4.66	0.746	0.815	0.871
GRU	8.3	4.94	0.71	0.545	0.861
SVR	5.54	3.55	0.871	0.815	0.935

Table 31: Volumetric Model Performance - Kander - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	20.13	74.19	5.35
XGBoost	-0.25%	-17.55%	-2.24%
LightGBM	-0.25%	-17.40%	-0.93%
MLP	-3.03%	-4.16%	11.03%
LSTM	-1.04%	-11.55%	-14.02%
GRU	-0.15%	-26.90%	14.21%
SVR	-1.19%	-15.43%	-4.30%

Table 32: Volumetric Model Performance - Kander - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	20.9	68.04	5.48
XGBoost	-3.64%	-9.41%	4.93%
LightGBM	-3.54%	-9.83%	5.84%
MLP	-7.56%	8.80%	0.91%
LSTM	-6.51%	-7.73%	-8.94%
GRU	-10.81%	-21.24%	20.07%
SVR	-4.16%	-8.45%	1.82%

Verzasca

Table 33: Performance metrics - Verzasca - 1990 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.86	0.89	-
XGBoost	6.99	2.77	0.844	0.782	0.919
LightGBM	6.74	2.86	0.855	0.825	0.925
MLP	7.62	3.35	0.814	0.891	0.909
LSTM	12.21	5.03	0.524	0.543	0.728
GRU	12.47	5.06	0.504	0.515	0.713
SVR	8.71	3.52	0.758	0.655	0.872

Table 34: Performance metrics - Verzasca - 1990 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	5.89	2.61	0.874	0.798	0.936
LightGBM	6.39	2.82	0.851	0.795	0.923
MLP	7.09	3.8	0.817	0.765	0.909
LSTM	11.71	5.04	0.501	0.433	0.708
GRU	11.98	5.68	0.478	0.436	0.696
SVR	6.65	3.32	0.839	0.765	0.917

Table 35: Volumetric Model Performance - Verzasca - 1990 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	9.9	91.26	1.35
XGBoost	-0.61%	-6.82%	1.48%
LightGBM	-0.51%	-4.56%	-0.74%
MLP	5.66%	8.59%	47.41%
LSTM	4.95%	-20.99%	-31.11%
GRU	0.10%	-22.28%	-55.56%
SVR	1.11%	-13.57%	-13.33%

Table 36: Volumetric Model Performance - Verzasca - 1990 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	10.63	88.19	1.53
XGBoost	-3.29%	-3.84%	4.58%
LightGBM	-2.54%	-4.20%	-10.46%
MLP	14.49%	-6.11%	136.60%
LSTM	1.79%	-32.38%	13.07%
GRU	11.19%	-34.06%	86.93%
SVR	-1.03%	-9.47%	-1.31%

Ticino

Table 37: Performance metrics - Ticino - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.87	0.92	-
XGBoost	25.98	15.74	0.821	0.71	0.908
LightGBM	26.54	16.35	0.813	0.749	0.902
MLP	28.2	15.71	0.789	0.663	0.893
LSTM	38.97	18.85	0.598	0.558	0.775
GRU	40.91	19.99	0.556	0.513	0.755
SVR	29.02	15.62	0.777	0.693	0.883

Table 38: Performance metrics - Ticino - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	25.18	15.65	0.798	0.688	0.899
LightGBM	23.88	14.93	0.819	0.729	0.908
MLP	21.74	14.56	0.85	0.867	0.922
LSTM	33.84	17.93	0.636	0.504	0.8
GRU	33.37	17.54	0.646	0.584	0.807
SVR	23.14	14.35	0.83	0.684	0.917

Table 39: Volumetric Model Performance - Ticino - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	63.35	313.76	18.89
XGBoost	-2.83%	-9.60%	27.10%
LightGBM	-1.56%	-8.94%	18.85%
MLP	-6.79%	1.09%	46.64%
LSTM	-5.48%	-17.09%	30.86%
GRU	-10.89%	-21.82%	17.58%
SVR	-3.13%	-9.49%	23.66%

Table 40: Volumetric Model Performance - Ticino - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	65.02	276.51	18.71
XGBoost	-7.21%	-5.60%	38.91%
LightGBM	-5.54%	-5.94%	38.48%
MLP	-2.21%	3.42%	56.01%
LSTM	-1.26%	-17.67%	62.80%
GRU	-6.06%	-15.92%	26.46%
SVR	-6.12%	-8.33%	45.54%

Broye

Table 41: Performance metrics - Broye - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.76	0.88	-
XGBoost	4.49	2.04	0.804	0.746	0.897
LightGBM	4.66	2.13	0.79	0.806	0.889
MLP	5.2	2.34	0.737	0.846	0.865
LSTM	7.13	3.34	0.506	0.531	0.716
GRU	7.5	3.77	0.455	0.55	0.697
SVR	4.47	2.3	0.806	0.763	0.898

Table 42: Performance metrics - Broye - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	4.44	2.03	0.826	0.832	0.909
LightGBM	4.24	1.98	0.841	0.829	0.917
MLP	4.63	2.03	0.81	0.756	0.901
LSTM	7.26	3.37	0.534	0.545	0.733
GRU	7.4	3.29	0.516	0.469	0.719
SVR	4.09	2	0.852	0.808	0.923

Table 43: Volumetric Model Performance - Broye - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	7.62	51.46	1.17
XGBoost	-0.13%	-10.92%	23.08%
LightGBM	0.26%	-8.20%	0.85%
MLP	-3.02%	-4.78%	34.19%
LSTM	3.94%	-24.14%	47.86%
GRU	14.70%	-13.16%	142.74%
SVR	0.92%	-6.32%	8.55%

Table 44: Volumetric Model Performance - Broye - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	8.13	54.3	1.34
XGBoost	2.21%	-7.24%	0.00%
LightGBM	2.21%	-8.86%	0.00%
MLP	-3.08%	-1.73%	4.48%
LSTM	1.11%	-20.81%	-14.93%
GRU	-2.83%	-27.57%	22.39%
SVR	-0.86%	-9.61%	19.40%

Thur

Table 45: Performance metrics - Thur - 1984 - 2015

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
PREVAH	-	-	0.9	0.94	-
XGBoost	19.74	10.25	0.856	0.796	0.926
LightGBM	19.93	10.51	0.854	0.808	0.924
MLP	21.58	10.54	0.828	0.857	0.912
LSTM	38.54	18.94	0.453	0.463	0.678
GRU	40.61	20.92	0.393	0.506	0.65
SVR	25.33	10.8	0.764	0.735	0.874

Table 46: Performance metrics - Thur - 1981 - 2020

Model	RMSE	MAE	NSE	KGE	r
XGBoost	16.48	9.18	0.892	0.912	0.945
LightGBM	17.68	9.9	0.875	0.937	0.938
MLP	17.2	9.37	0.882	0.941	0.941
LSTM	36.12	19.19	0.48	0.56	0.703
GRU	36.84	19.56	0.459	0.45	0.68
SVR	17.02	9.69	0.884	0.919	0.941

Table 47: Volumetric Model Performance - Thur - 1984 - 2015

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	45.3	243.1	8.79
XGBoost	0.46%	-6.07%	-10.58%
LightGBM	0.60%	-7.61%	-3.75%
MLP	4.44%	2.63%	34.47%
LSTM	4.04%	-15.11%	19.34%
GRU	7.00%	-13.10%	-46.19%
SVR	-0.60%	-4.80%	13.88%

Table 48: Volumetric Model Performance - Thur - 1981 - 2020

	Mean	99 th Percentile	5 th Percentile
Measurement	48.44	249.75	10.33
XGBoost	-1.20%	-4.40%	-1.26%
LightGBM	-0.89%	-2.65%	1.65%
MLP	-0.19%	1.05%	3.39%
LSTM	2.27%	-13.15%	16.07%
GRU	1.01%	-27.74%	20.62%
SVR	-1.07%	-6.31%	6.29%

5.2. Hydrographs

This section first presents regime plots for each algorithm sorted by catchment for both calibration/validation splits (Figures 12 - 29). Monthly mean discharge hydrographs are then presented to give an overview of the model performance during the validation periods (Figures 30 - 47). Lastly, the daily mean discharge over a four-month period is presented for the Plessur and the Thur exemplarily, to showcase a catchment heavily influenced by melting processes and one mainly influenced by rainfall respectively (Figures 48 - 51). The corresponding figures of the remaining catchments can be found in Annex B.

All models can reproduce the general shape of the regime. However, there are large differences between the algorithms. The reason for looking at the regime plots (Figures 12 - 29) is that they provide more generalised information. The long-term monthly average is not strongly influenced by single flood events and therefore acts as an indicator of how good the general volumetric performance is during a specific month and thus the model's ability to reproduce the seasonality. A visual inspection shows that the regression forest-based models either accurately estimate (Thur, Verzasca) or underestimate (Emme, Rosegbach, Kander) the peak of the regime (e.g. Figures 14 & 15). In some catchments (Plessur, Venoge, Ticino, Broje) one of the two calibration / validation splits accurately estimates the peak while the other model underestimates it. Apart from the peak they often follow the measured regime closely (e.g. Figures 22 & 23). The regime plot of the SVR based models is similar to the regression forest-based models (e.g. Figures 12, 16, 18). The peak month is often underestimated, while the models fit the rest of the years better. Although visually very similar, the SVR based models appears to perform slightly worse. While the above models tend to underestimate the peak, the neural network-based models are not so easy to generalise. The MLP based models overestimate the peaks in some cases (e.g. Figures 13 & 23), model them quite well in others (e.g. Figures 18 & 29) or underestimate it (e.g. Figure 17) with no clear pattern. The models based on recurrent networks perform inconsistently. They overestimate (e.g. Figure 14) and underestimate (e.g. Figure 16) peaks. While the general shape of the modelled regime fits most of the time, it is often shifted up or down compared to the measured regime (e.g. Figures 23, 24, 26). They are the only algorithms that produce regimes with larger errors, except for the underestimation of peak months (e.g. Figures 12 & 18), with the GRU-based models showing the largest errors.

Looking at the hydrographs showing the monthly mean discharge (Figures 30 - 47), it can be seen that the neural network and especially the recurrent RNN-based models tend to have the biggest monthly mean discharge, most notably during peak periods. This is consistent with the findings from the regime plots. It is worth noting that all algorithms perform better in modelling peaks of monthly mean discharge in catchments dominated by precipitation than in catchments dominated by melting processes. Looking at the monthly mean discharge during the years used in both validation periods (1995, 2001, 2007, 2013), no effect of the different calibration periods on strongly over- or underestimated peaks can be observed.

Figure 48 to 51 show the daily mean discharge of the catchments Plessur and Thur. All models are able to mimic the general shape of the measured hydrograph of the Plessur (Figures 48 & 49). On closer inspection of the figures, however, it becomes clear that the individual peaks are poorly captured by all models. The hydrograph of the RNN-based models looks smoothed. They predict the beginning of a peak more or less accurately, but the timing of the maxima is off by a few days. The same is true for the declining part of the peak. Looking at the hydrograph of the Thur, however, the models, except for the RNN-based models do a strikingly better job at capturing even small peaks. Here it becomes even more evident that the peaks of the RNN-based models are delayed by a few days and seem to be

smoothed. Visually, all except the RNN-based models seem to perform slightly better with an extended calibration period. However, in the second half of April, it is noticeable that the artificial peak becomes visible in more models.

Figure 13: Emme – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 14: Emme – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 15: Plessur – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 16: Plessur – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 – 2020

Figure 17: Rosebach – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 18: Rosebach – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 – 2020

Figure 19: Venoge – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 20: Venoge – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 21: Kander – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 22: Kander – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 23: Verzasca – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1990 - 2015

Figure 24: Verzasca – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1990 – 2020

Figure 25: Ticino – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 26: Ticino – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 27: Broye – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 28: Broye – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 – 2020

Figure 29: Thur – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 30: Thur – Long term monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 31: Emme - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 32: Emme - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 33: Plessur - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 34: Plessur - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 35: Rosebach - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 36: Rosebach - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 37: Venoge - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 38: Venoge - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 39: Kander - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 40: Kander - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 41: Verzasca - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1990 - 2015

Figure 42: Verzasca - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1990 - 2020

Figure 43: Ticino - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 44: Ticino - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 45: Broye - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 46: Broye - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 47: Thur - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1984 - 2015

Figure 48: Thur - Monthly mean discharge with validation period 1981 - 2020

Figure 49: Plessur - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 50: Plessur - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 - 2020

Figure 51: Thur - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 52: Thur - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 - 2020

6. Discussion

In this section the research questions are answered by interpreting the results and comparing them to literature. Furthermore, the used methods are discussed critically.

One aim of this study was to compare 6 different machine learning models with the conceptual model PREVAH in Muelchi et al. (2020), which serves as a benchmark model. Comparing the performance metrics of the ML models used in this study with those of the benchmark model PREVAH in Muelchi et al. (2020), it can be seen that the NSE value of the PREVAH model in Muelchi et al. (2020) was reached in three catchments (Rosegbach, Verzasca, Broje) by XGBoost, LightGBM, SVR, and in one case the MLP model, using the same data for calibration and validation. The KGE values of the PREVAH models in Muelchi et al. (2020) could only be reached by the MLP model at the Verzasca. The LSTM and GRU based models are clearly outperformed by PREVAH and all other ML algorithms used in this study. Even though the performance metrics of the benchmark model in Muelchi et al. (2020) could be equalled or surpassed a few times, it performs much more consistent and on a high level. The very good performance of PREVAH in Muelchi et al. (2020) regarding the KGE values indicates that PREVAH is in particular better at modelling the variability of discharge as the KGE gives greater consideration to a correct representation of the variability. However, when the ML models are being calibrated with an extended calibration period, their performance increases with some of the models reaching similar values (within 0.01 after rounding) or outperforming PREVAH regarding the NSE in all catchments but Plessur. The KGE values on the other hand remain mostly below those of PREVAH even with the extended calibration period. It is unclear whether PREVAH would also profit from a longer calibration period as no study looking into this aspect could be found. Also, in other studies (Zappa & Kan, 2007; Addor et al., 2014), the PREVAH model performed worse than in Muelchi et al. (2020). Comparing the ML models to the performance metrics of PREVAH in those studies the regression forest-based models outperform PREVAH consistently while the SVR based models perform similarly. It is assumed that the performance differences of PREVAH in the different studies is due to differences in the parameter optimisation during calibration. In this regard when comparing the results of this study with the results of Muelchi et al. (2020), it should be kept in mind that the MSE was used as a loss function in this study while Muelchi et al. (2020) used a mixture of discharge, transformed discharge, monthly mean discharge, and yearly volume. This much more sophisticated loss function might indirectly benefit a high KGE value. Using a more complex or the same loss function for the ML models would allow a better comparability between the studies. This suggests that good hyperparameter optimisation is not only important to ML models but also for conceptual models. All algorithms except SVR allow the implementation of custom loss functions. Testing these, however, was outside the scope of this study. Another approach to further improve the ML models is to provide additional input data such as minimum and maximum daily temperature, or the elevation of the zero-degree limit.

Compared to other studies, the model performance of the XGBoost models is in a similar range (Szczepanek, 2022; Wang et al., 2022) or better depending on the study design (Wang & Peng, 2024). The same holds for LightGBM (Szczepanek, 2022; Cui et al., 2021). The model performance of the MLP and SVR models is in a similar range compared to literature (Senthil Kumar et al., 2005; Chiang et al., 2022) or better (Botsis et al., 2011). The LSTM based models in this study performed worse compared to literature (Cui et al., 2021; Gao et al., 2020; Kratzert et al., 2018; Kratzert et al., 2019; Kratzert et al., 2021). Like the LSTM based models the GRU based models in this study performed

worse to comparable studies (Gao et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Yokoo et al., 2021). The potential reason for the underperformance of the RNN based algorithms are discussed later in this section.

As for the question if and how different catchment characteristics influence the performance of the different ML algorithms, it can be seen that GRU and LSTM based models perform clearly better in catchments which are dominated by melt processes. As mentioned in the results section the RNN based models fail to accurately predict the timing and magnitude of the peak discharges. In meltwater dominated catchments the contribution of rainfall to the peak discharge is smaller in relation to rainfall dominated catchments. Thus, these shortcomings have a smaller influence on the performance metrics. When looking for example at the QQ-plot of the LSTM model for the Plessur catchment (Figure 53) it becomes apparent that

Figure 53: QQ-Plot of the LSTM model of the Plessur catchment

despite a KGE of 0.86 the modelled maximum discharge is cut off at the 99th percentile of the measured discharge (the 99th percentile is indicated by the horizontal line) and the rest of the upper percentiles is overestimated which is not an indication for a good model.

SVR based models tend to perform better in meltwater dominated catchments. This effect is stronger when calibrated on the shorter period. One reason for this is probably the effect that also explains the better performance of RNN-based models in meltwater-dominated catchments. The MLP based models show no difference based on catchment characteristics when looking at the NSE values. When looking at the KGE values on the other hand, it can be seen that they perform better in rainfall dominated catchments. XGBoost and LightGBM do not show clear differences in NSE and KGE values depending on catchment characteristics.

An advantage of regression forest-based models over other ML models is that they are relatively easy to interpret. The regression trees allow to calculate the importance of each input variable. This can be used to derive important information about the behaviour of a catchment, such as the response time to precipitation or the main processes generating discharge. The importance of an input variable is based on how often it is used to determine the path on the decision trees given a set of data. Thus, the importance not only depends on the model but also on the input data and does not necessarily reflect the absolute contribution of an input variable on the discharge. Figure 54 shows an example of the importance of the input parameters of the LightGBM model for the Thur catchment. It can be seen that precipitation plays a much greater role than temperature in predicting discharge in the Thur catchment in the LGBM-based models. It suggests that the parameter “precipitation lagged by one day” is the most important, meaning that most of the time discharge generated by precipitation reaches the gauge on the next day. In addition, the sum of precipitation over the last four to seven days also seems to play a role. This information sounds plausible, given that the Thur is a lowland river.

Figure 54: Input parameter importance: LightGBM Thur

Figure 55: Input parameter importance: LightGBM Kander

Figure 55 shows the importance plot of the LightGBM model for the Kander. Temperature plays a much larger role than for the Thur. The high importance of the mean temperature of the last seven days and the mean temperature of the second last month indicate that the catchment is influenced by meltwater processes. At the same time, precipitation lagged by one day also plays a role. Given that this is a more mountainous catchment, this is also plausible. However, this information is influenced by the distribution of the input data. Rare events are underrepresented, while 'average' conditions have a large influence.

Another question aimed to answer in this study is the influence of an extended calibration period on the model performance. As described in the results section, in general performance metrics improve with an extended calibration period. The performance gain of the regression forest-based model can be explained by how the algorithms work. They build complex decision trees on how to group the data based on the predictors. With increasing data points in the training data, the likelihood of containing similar datapoints to the one to be predicted increases and thus the model's capacity to allocate similar datapoints to each other. The exact reason for the improvement of the neural network-based model is harder to pin down. Generally, the neural networks capacity to generalize increases with diverse training data, allowing it to better predict new data points. When comparing the two calibration periods it needs to be taken into account that different years were used for validation. Meaning the validation periods can or cannot contain particularly difficult years to predict respectively and therefore influence the performance metrics.

As mentioned above the RNN based model underperform in this study compared to the literature (Kratzert et al., 2019; Cui et al., 2021). It is assumed that this is likely due to a non-identifiable programming issue as the hyperparameter "timesteps" of the RNN models was consistently optimised towards the lower boundary when trained on all derived input variables. When only trained on the daily precipitation sum and daily mean temperature the optimal value for the HP "time steps" was around 60 with the model performance dropping even lower. In this study the lower optimisation boundary was fixed at five timesteps because smaller numbers defeat the purpose of RNNs. Kratzert et

al. (2019) determined 270 as an optimal value for the hyperparameter “time steps” in their study, reaching NSE values above 0.8 in approximately 30% of their modelled catchments (n= 531). In another study Kratzert et al. (2021) showed that LSTM perform better on regionalized models than on individual catchments.

Even though the HP optimisation of the random forest-based models was performed using cross validation, the models overfit during the calibration period, consistently reaching NSE and KGE values of over 0.99 (see Figure 56). Usually, an overfitting during calibration leads to a bad model performance with validation data. In this case however, the models are still among the best performing ones.

Figure 56: QQ-plot of the calibration period: LightGBM Broye

7. Conclusion

The objective of this study was to investigate the performance of six machine learning algorithms (XGBoost, LightGBM, MLP, LSTM, GRU, SVR) in rainfall runoff modelling in nine Swiss catchments. Furthermore, the study aimed to evaluate the performance of the algorithms based on different catchment characteristics and the amount of training data. To compare the results of this study, the results of Muelchi et al. (2020) obtained with the PREVAH model were used as a benchmark. While some of the models used in this study managed to outperform the NSE values of Muelchi et al. (2020) in some cases, no ML algorithm was as consistent as the benchmark model. The KGE values could only be reached in 3 cases. However, when looking at other studies than Muelchi et al. (2020) using PREVAH to model discharge (Zappa & Kan, 2007; Addor et al., 2014) on the same catchments the XGBoost and LightGBM models consistently outperform PREVAH. This emphasizes the importance of good model calibration and hyper parameter optimisation. Using ML algorithms, the difference between different optimised models is often smaller than between non-optimised and optimised models (Szczepanek, 2022).

XGBoost and LightGBM were the most consistent and produced the best results most of the time. The SVR and MLP models followed slightly after and the LSTM and GRU performing worst. The results suggest that despite the bad performance of the RNN-based models ML can be an effective tool for rainfall runoff modelling in Swiss catchments.

The key challenge faced was the optimisation of the RNN-based models. As discussed above the discharge peaks of these models are delayed and underestimated and the optimal timestep variable was always at the minimum of the set optimisation range, effectively removing the key feature of the RNNs. Additionally, the comparison of the two calibration periods was not set up optimally and an effect of the different years used in the validation on the results cannot be ruled out. Also, this case study is based on only 9 catchments. To gain a more robust understanding of how the ML algorithms perform, a comparison with all 93 catchments used in Muelchi et al. (2020) would be a good approach. In addition, it would be interesting to see if the ML models perform better with the NSE and / or KGE as loss function as well as with additional input variables as for example minimum and maximum temperature or the zero-degree limit. Furthermore, a closer look at the neural network structures could lead to improvements in performance or training speed. It was decided in this study to keep the number of nodes used in each layer of a model constant. Using a decreasing number of nodes in each consecutive layer might speed up the training without losing predictive performance. It is also possible to stack layers of different ML algorithms in a model to potentially benefit from their different strengths. Lastly, for larger catchments, it would be interesting to see if dividing them into sub-catchments and linking them to each other would increase the overall performance at the cost of additional training time.

With the ML algorithms being so flexible regarding the used input variables and the temporal resolution it is difficult to find studies with the same setup and similar optimisation. This flexibility can be a great advantage, but it also makes it difficult to compare the results of different studies or to choose the right algorithm for a specific use case. To help making algorithm selection easier, the strength and weakness based on the results of this study are summarized in Table 49 below.

Table 49: Advantages and disadvantages of the used ML algorithms

Algorithm	Strengths	Weaknesses
XGBoost	Short training time, input variable importance analysis, consistent performance	Modelled value range only within training data range
LightGBM	Short training time, input variable importance analysis, consistent performance	Modelled value range only within training data range, much more hyperparameter than other algorithms: selection for HPO needed
MLP	Ability to model outside of training data range, best performance (KGE) in rainfall dominated catchments	Medium training time, non-continuous hyper parameters
LSTM	Ability to model outside of training data range	Long training time, delayed discharge peaks, non-continuous hyper parameters, difficult HPO
GRU	Ability to model outside of training data range	Long training time, delayed discharge peaks, non-continuous hyper parameters, difficult HPO
SVR	Ability to model outside of training data range, similar performance to XGboost and LightGBM with sufficient training data length	Nonlinear increase of complexity with increase of input variables, currently no implementation of multi-threading on Windows, strongest influence of calibration period length on model performance, no custom loss function possible

8. Literature

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9. Annex

The source code used for this thesis as well as all plots and results are available on GitHub (<https://github.com/ben-mey/RainfallRunnoffModel>).

10. A

Hyperparameters used for the XGBoost models:

Table 50: Optimized Hyperparameter set used for XGBoost models

Catchment	Max depth	Eta	Alpha	Lambda	Min child weight	nrounds
Ticino	10	0.143	3.73	5.64	20	250
Broye	9	0.092	4.32	9.93	9	250
Thur	7	0.0714	9.1	3.8	3	250
Emme	8	0.164	12	1	1	250
Plessur	12	0.159	5.04	11.7	23	250
Rosegbach	9	0.092	4.32	9.93	9	250
Venoge	9	0.092	4.32	9.93	9	250
Kander	8	0.187	1.97	6.12	5	250
Verzasca	10	0.143	3.73	5.64	21	250
Emme S	5	0.25	1	8.75	1	236
Plessur S	12	0.0788	12	1	15	250
Rosegbach S	9	0.092	4.32	9.93	9	250
Venoge S	9	0.092	4.32	9.93	9	250
Kander S	10	0.143	3.73	5.64	21	250
Verzasca S	7	0.0714	9.1	3.8	3	250
Ticino S	12	0.0801	12	1	13	250
Broye S	10	0.143	3.73	5.64	21	250
Thur S	4	0.195	2.63	1.54	26	249

Hyperparameter used for the LightGBM models:

Table 51: Optimized Hyperparameter set used for LightGBM models

Catchment	Max depth	Eta	Num leaves	Min data in leaf	nrounds
Ticino	9	0.0633	150	5	200
Broye	8	0.108	65	15	200
Thur	11	0.201	59	14	200
Emme	15	0.118	120	5	200
Plessur	15	0.0451	150	5	200
Rosegbach	11	0.201	59	14	200
Venoge	9	0.154	62	15	197
Kander	15	0.0413	150	5	200
Verzasca	6	0.219	20	31	200
Emme S	8	0.108	65	15	200
Plessur S	15	0.121	150	5	197
Rosegbach S	11	0.201	59	14	200
Venoge S	9	0.166	41	21	200
Kander S	13	0.0476	150	5	200
Verzasca S	11	0.201	59	14	199
Ticino S	11	0.201	59	14	200
Broye S	12	0.245	13	19	197
Thur S	12	0.245	13	19	199

Hyperparameter used for the SVR models:

Table 52: Optimized Hyperparameter set used for SVR models

Catchment	Epsilon	Cost
Ticino	0.307	5.11
Broye	0.105	8.69
Thur	0.199	8.34
Emme	0.154	4.76
Plessur	0.0769	16.5
Rosegbach	0.0486	8.78
Venoge	0.105	8.69
Kander	0.148	16.1
Verzasca	0.23	17.2
Emme S	0.005	8.19
Plessur S	0.0769	16.5
Rosegbach S	0.0107	22.7
Venoge S	0.23	17.2
Kander S	0.0885	11.2
Verzasca S	0.151	20.7
Ticino S	0.0769	16.5
Broye S	0.23	17.2
Thur S	0.0685	14.8

Hyperparameter used for the MLP models:

Table 53: Optimized Hyperparameter set used for MLP models

Catchment	Units	Layers	Dropout	Batchsize	Learningrate
Ticino	101	4	0	78	0.00282
Broye	81	2	0.139	133	0.001
Thur	120	3	0.203	80	0.00226
Emme	84	3	0	90	0.001
Plessur	30	2	0.0535	105	0.00473
Rosegbach	150	3	0	103	0.00693
Venoge	98	2	0.092	56	0.00351
Kander	71	2	0	150	0.00838
Verzasca	25	2	0	5	0.001
Emme S	30	2	0.0535	105	0.00473
Plessur S	52	3	0.0267	14	0.00816
Rosegbach S	150	4	0.137	5	0.001
Venoge S	70	3	0.0499	148	0.0105
Kander S	63	2	0.0358	117	0.00562
Verzasca S	150	1	0.4	41	0.00352
Ticino S	107	1	0.351	140	0.00746
Broye S	125	3	0.0732	143	0.00581
Thur S	127	1	0	5	0.001

Hyperparameter used for the LSTM models:

Table 54: Optimized Hyperparameter set used for LSTM models

Catchment	Units	Layers	Dropout	Batchsize	Timesteps	Learningrate
Ticino	64	4	0	5	5	0.0116
Broye	140	4	0.0595	5	5	0.0145
Thur	85	3	0	5	5	0.015
Emme	150	1	0	5	5	0.015
Plessur	124	3	0	39	5	0.015
Rosegbach	97	4	0.03	150	5	0.015
Venoge	150	4	0.0202	91	5	0.00864
Kander	108	4	0.14	5	5	0.015
Verzasca	150	1	0	5	5	0.015
Emme S	150	1	0	5	5	0.015
Plessur S	82	4	0	5	5	0.015
Rosegbach S	150	3	0	5	5	0.015
Venoge S	150	4	0	150	5	0.015
Kander S	150	4	0	5	5	0.015
Verzasca S	150	3	5	68	5	0.015
Ticino S	150	1	0	5	5	0.015
Broye S	150	1	0	5	5	0.015
Thur S	150	3	0	5	5	0.015

Hyperparameter used for the GRU models:

Table 55: Optimized Hyperparameter set used for GRU models

Catchment	Units	Layers	Dropout	Batchsize	Timesteps	Learningrate
Ticino	150	1	0	150	5	0.001
Broye	60	4	0	106	5	0.0135
Thur	150	3	0	150	5	0.00566
Emme	63	1	0	150	5	0.001
Plessur	150	3	0.119	56	5	0.001
Rosegbach	77	2	0.255	146	5	0.00691
Venoge	16	4	0	150	5	0.0108
Kander	83	4	0.208	150	5	0.00526
Verzasca	141	4	0	20	5	0.001
Emme S	66	4	0	69	5	0.001
Plessur S	150	3	0	150	5	0.00657
Rosegbach S	59	4	0	150	5	0.0133
Venoge S	61	4	0.172	150	5	0.00337
Kander S	58	4	0	150	5	0.00877
Verzasca S	150	1	0	150	5	0.001
Ticino S	64	3	0	92	5	0.00459
Broye S	108	4	0	67	5	0.00417
Thur S	108	1	0	150	5	0.00579

11. B

Figure 57: Emme - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 58: Emme - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 - 2020

Figure 59: Rosegbach - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 60: Rosegbach - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 - 2020

Figure 61: Venoge - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 62: Venoge - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 - 2020

Figure 63: Kander - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 64: Kander - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 - 2020

Figure 65: Verzasca - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1990 - 2015

Figure 66: Verzasca - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1990 - 2020

Figure 67: Ticino - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 68: Ticino - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 - 2020

Figure 69: Broye - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1984 - 2015

Figure 70: Broye - Daily mean discharge with calibration period 1981 – 2020

Declaration of Consent

on the basis of Article 30 of the RSL Phil.-nat. 18

Name/First Name: Meyer Benjamin

Registration Number: 11-636-362

Study program: Geography Master Major 90 ECTS, SP2016
Ecology and Evolution Master Minor 30 ECTS, SP2005/2008

Bachelor

Master

Dissertation

Title of the thesis: Performance of Different Machine Learning Algorithms in Rainfall Runoff Modelling Compared to the Conceptual Model PREVAH in Selected Swiss Catchments

Supervisor: Dr. Pascal Horton

I declare herewith that this thesis is my own work and that I have not used any sources other than those stated. I have indicated the adoption of quotations as well as thoughts taken from other authors as such in the thesis. I am aware that the Senate pursuant to Article 36 paragraph 1 litera r of the University Act of 5 September, 1996 is authorized to revoke the title awarded on the basis of this thesis.

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